

One-Way Journey or Returning Home in the Novel the Path of the Eels by Luan Starova

Seyhan MURTEZAN İBRAHİMİ*

ABSTRACT

Globalization is a historical and dialectical process encompassing various cultural elements and dimensions applicable globally, yet inherently characteristic of specific regions and cultures. The Balkans is a region where multiple cultures have interacted, evolved and coexisted over time. In the past, the Balkans were ruled and influenced by many empires; as a result, the region witnessed countless bloody battles. Despite a turbulent and often difficult past, the Balkans have managed to foster cohesion and bring together the states and communities of the region. This research analyzes the concept of a one-way journey and migratory landmarks. Throughout human history, the Earth has been the only homeland that remains unchanged and does not undergo transformation. This paper interprets the novel *The Path of the Eels* by the Albanian writer Luan Starova, through Stuart Hall's assertion that Migration is a one-way journey. There is no "nest" to return to. The novel offers a literary exploration of identity. Through *The Path of the Eels*, the study examines themes of exposure and boundaries—standing at the threshold and hearing the sounds from the other side of the border. It explores how collective identity is formed and represented from a perspective rooted in the past rather than the present. The study also explores the idea of crossing a threshold—stepping beyond the border and entering, conditionally speaking, the 'ordered' world of norms and civilization.

Keywords: Migration, Exile, Identity, Novel.

Assoc. Prof. Dr., International Balkan University, Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Sciences, Skopje, North Macedonia, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0287-4073, smibrahimi@ibu.edu.mk
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Luan Starova'nın Yılan Balığı Yolu Romanında Tek Yönlü Yolculuk veya Eve Dönüş

Seyhan MURTEZAN İBRAHİMİ*

ÖZET

Küreselleşme, tarihsel ve diyalektik bir süreç olarak, evrensel ölçekte geçerli olabilen, ancak aynı zamanda belirli bölge ve kültürlerle özgü karakteristikler taşıyan çeşitli kültürel unsurları ve boyutları kapsamaktadır. Bu bağlamda, Balkanlar; çoklu kültürlerin tarih boyunca etkileşime geçtiği, evrildiği ve bir arada var olduğu nadir bölgelerden biridir. Geçmişte pek çok imparatorluğun hâkimiyeti altına giren bu coğrafya, sayısız kanlı çatışmaya tanıklık etmiştir. Tüm bu çalkantılı ve çoğu zaman yıkıcı geçmişine rağmen, Balkanlar farklı devlet ve topluluklar arasında bir tür toplumsal uyum ve dayanışma zemini yaratmayı başarmıştır. Bu çalışma, tek yönlü yolculuk kavramını ve göçün sembolik eşiklerini analiz etmektedir. İnsanlık tarihi boyunca dünya, dönüşü olmayan göçlerin sabit ve değişmeyen yegâne yurdu olarak kabul edilegelmiştir. Bu bağlamda, Arnavut yazar Luan Starova'nın Yılanbalıklarının Yolu adlı romanı, Stuart Hall'un "Göç tek yönlü bir yolculuktur; geri dönülecek bir yuva yoktur" önermesi çerçevesinde yorumlanmaktadır. Roman, kimlik olgusunu edebi bir zemin üzerinden irdelemektedir. Çalışma, Yılan Balıklarının Yolu aracılığıyla, sınırdırma hâlini, öte yakadan gelen sesleri duyma deneyimini ve maruz kalma ile sınırları aşma temalarını incelemektedir. Bu bağlamda, kolektif kimliğin nasıl geçmişe dayalı olarak inşa edildiği ve temsil edildiği ele alınmaktadır. Aynı zamanda, eşikten geçme—simgesel anlamda sınırın ötesine adım atarak 'düzenli' normlar ve medeniyet dünyasına giriş—fikri de sorgulanmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Göç, Sürgün, Kimlik, Roman.

Assoc. Prof. Dr., International Balkan University, Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Sciences, Skopje, North Macedonia, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0287-4073, smibrahimi@ibu.edu.mk
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1. INTRODUCTION

“Migration is a one-way journey.

There is no nest to return to.”

— Stuart Hall

Literary works from the Balkans, a region long ruled by the Ottoman Empire, primarily focus on the period of the empire’s expansion as well as its eventual withdrawal from these territories. As the Ottoman Empire receded from the Balkans, the remaining populations faced the challenge of shaping their identities and understanding perceptions of otherness.

Differences in beliefs, cultural transformation and ways of life lie at the core of this identity crisis. Luan Starova connects this process to his entire life experience. His family has always been marked by the powerful turbulences of history, exile, and unpredictable fate. Since the 1940s, Starova’s family—both close and extended—has been carried by waves of exile; some were forced to find refuge by crossing lakes (his parents), while others had to cross seas and oceans.

Starova spent his entire life at the crossroads between the West and the East, between the two sides of the Lake Ohrid, dedicating all his intellectual energy and imagination to tracking his family’s fate, and even the fate of the Balkan people. This journey is reflected in his work *Balkanovavilonci* (Балкановавилонци), which was awarded the Novel of the Year in 2014. As he narrates, Laun Arif Starova began his career as a journalist, serving as editor-in-chief of the weekly *Mlad Borec* (“Young Fighter”), working at Radio Skopje, and later directing the Albanian program on TV-Skopje. Since 1974, after earning his master’s and doctorate in modern French literature and specializing at the “New Sorbonne,” he pursued a career as a university professor of French literature at the Faculty of Philology “Blazhe Koneski” in Skopje. He also held diplomatic posts, an Ambassador of SFR Yugoslavia to Tunisia and the State of Palestine, the first ambassador of the Republic of

Macedonia to France, a permanent representative to UNESCO, and a non-resident ambassador to Spain and Portugal (Старова, 2014).

Luan Starova is an author who lived between two cultures, shaped by diverse linguistic and cultural influences. He had a long diplomatic career and was a polyglot who spoke six languages. Throughout his journey, he was profoundly influenced by the metaphysical ideas in his father's library, whose distinctive layout symbolized more than just a family past; it became a lens through which he viewed his own work. Starova shed light on this labyrinth of the exile in his Balkan Saga, stating: "... already torn between Ottoman Turkey and Atatürk's Turkey, between Albania and the challenges of Balkan exile, which ultimately prevailed in the early 1940s, when, moving from one shore of the lake to the other, within a micro-space of three hundred kilometers, we became perpetual emigrants forever" (Старова, 2013a, p. 15).

Fethi Bey (Okyar), uncle of Starova's father's, played a significant role in shaping the life journey of this family. He was one of the key collaborators of Kemal Atatürk. He acted as an intermediary for his father's meeting with Atatürk, during which he was offered various positions to remain in Istanbul. For a period of time, Starova's father was part of the judicial hierarchy of a newly established Turkish Republic, having graduated law and Islamic philosophy. In an interview conducted with the author in 2015, he refers to his ancestors with the following description:

My paternal grandmother Hazbiye, first cousin of Ali Fethi Okyar, with whom she had a brotherly relationship (both died in 1943), belonged to a prominent Turkish family from Prilep. When her family moved to Turkey at the end of the 19th century, Grandma Hazbiye became the wife of my grandfather Ahmed-bey from Pogradec. My Turkish grandmother, although a kind of "orphan" in relation to her departed family in Turkey, torn from her own, would bring light and hope to our family, a kind of human crystallization of Ottoman culture and civilization... My father was the true heir to Grandma's Turkish language, especially when he studied Law and

Islamic Philosophy in Istanbul, with his uncle Ali Fethi Okyar (Ибрахими, 2015, p. 82)

Starova uses his family history to illustrate the complex and often conflicting forces that shape identity in the Balkans, particularly the conflict between inherited belonging and the need to adapt to changing historical circumstances. For Starova, as for Stuart Hall, identity is not a fixed entity, but a process of constant negotiation between the past and the present. Starova's paternal grandmother, Hazbiye, a Turkish woman from Prilep, represents a cultural inheritance rooted in the Ottoman Empire. Though she brought "light and hope" to the family, she also remained somewhat separated, "torn from her own" family that had emigrated to Turkey. This sense of separation, of being an "orphan" in relation to her departed family, embodies the broader experience of displacement and exile that permeates *The Path of the Eels*. The grandmother's treasured Turkish language and Istanbul magazines served as constant reminders of a cultural heritage that shaped the family's identity, even as they adapted to new circumstances. This inheritance, however, was not without its complexities. Inheriting his grandmother's Turkish language and culture, Starova's father eventually crossed the border and became a Yugoslav emigrant in Macedonia. This migration marked a break from the past and an adaptation to a new reality, yet he continued working in the State Archive of Macedonia, studying the Ottoman-era Bitola Kadi registers. This suggests that the past, even when seemingly left behind, continues to exert a powerful influence on the present, shaping identity and belonging in complex and often contradictory ways.

2. The "Betwixt" State: Migration and the Shifting Grounds of Identity in Starova's Narrative

In Luan Starova's writing, literature serves as a mirror that reflects reality, the forgotten time, memories, past and possible future states and events in the world and society where he lived. Since every work of art captures universal themes, while reflecting reality, it explains life in some way (Moran, 2017). Migration is one of those factors. It is a phenomenon that affects all societies and creates a bond between

history and humanity. The relocation of a person from their birthplace to a different environment brings great difficulties (Ayata, 2008). For the writer displaced to Macedonia, adapting to unfamiliar circumstances prompts a response that gradually forms a new identity.

The exile is a forcibly opened and unbridgeable space between a person and their birthplace or where they grew up, as well as between the self and the real nest of the self. According to Said (2016, p. 28) the sorrow at its core cannot be overcome. Every person who faced migration carries the sense of the unknown. This is primarily because of the concern and curiosity about where they are going, what challenges they will face, and how they will overcome them. It is profoundly difficult to feel lost in an unfamiliar corner of the world, feeling hopeless, when no one understands your language or knows your background.

With a blended identity and a deep sense of self, Luan Starova holds the key to unlocking new realms within his literary world. His narration reveals the hopelessness that forces us to see other stories, the controversy of the apparent completeness of the modern individual, alienation as well as the opportunity to understand the question of the inner foreigner, a concept introduced by the outsider, and one that internally undermines it. The sense of location and belonging, built during the transition alongside the migration, takes an endless shape and purpose in the writer's narrative. Migration, at its core, is a kind of "Betwixt" state. According to Chambers, the migrant experiences a sense of rootlessness caught between a past lost in distant worlds and a present that remains only partially integrated (Chambers, 2014, p. 48).

The concept of another "home," as an inevitable condition of the migrant experience, suggests a sense of belonging to the world; it means perceiving the place where one lives as a mobile habitat. The hope that each place is merely transitional, that there is a return home, putting an end to the story, finding a shorter path home, becomes impossible.

Even if it is true that everyone prevented from returning home is in exile, regardless of how well they adapt, they remain outsiders who perceive their loneli-

ness as a kind of orphanhood. Peace and tranquility are impossible to imagine alongside the condition of the persons in exile. Otherwise, how could Starova, banished from the place he was born, raised and rooted so easily accept the place where new accounts are settled as his new home? This is because we find him as someone whose roots are simultaneously uprooted and transplanted from the same reality. The major advantage of the context and classification of the culture we carry with us is that it allows us to reflect on them regardless of whether they exist or have ever existed there (Hall, 2017, p. 82).

As the sunset of life approaches, a person in these Balkan regions—at a small crossroads between West and East, such as the city of Skopje—stands at the crossroads of transience (Старова, 2013b, p. 9).

Starova tries to eliminate the state where he never had a place to call home, aligning it with his belonging in the field of literature. Because traveling from one place to other tears away a person from their roots, homeland, and tradition.

What does it feel like to dream that, almost until the end of your life, you will remain living in your birthplace - knowing that you truly belong there? This question has been present with Starova since his childhood.

Everyone in the family, in their own way, was obsessed with the enigma of returning to their homeland, but everyone was clear about our belonging. Father's disappearance left me poorer than the goodness and greatness of his opinion and parental protection, when in the spring of 1979 I was offered the opportunity to travel to Albania, to taste the return to the land of my roots. I was offered the opportunity to confirm or refute, not without a little risk, my father's experience that there is no real return from exile (Старова, 2013b, p. 30).

2.1. Historical Trauma and Uprooted Identities

In the novel *The Path of the Eels*, the author describes his family's tragic history. It is a book about 'uprooted families' whose identities fragment through

migration. This process, both literal and spiritual, ultimately gives birth to a new, complex sense of self, which is a source of hope.

When it comes to whether migration/exile is a one-way journey and whether there is still hope for return, we could say that the psychological state of the migrant, the pressure regarding identity, may cause fatal deviations, maybe even more than in any other aspects of life. Their journey to where they find themselves follows a path ignited by history, one they cannot avoid, much like an unavoidable traffic accident.

The novel *The Path of the Eels* is an unresolved metaphor of migration, the first direction of the journey. The signposts of what may be the eternal path toward a new life. In this novel, Starova tells the story of a family drama in which, from a young age, he flees from fascism and Stalinism, searching for his path, much like the eels navigating the river. According to Pierre-Robert Leclercq, this drama unfolds between the Father and the lake, where the Father follows the path of the eels that travel through great rivers to reach the oceans. Fleeing from fascism arriving from Italy, he and his family must confront the challenge of escaping the vicious Balkan cycle (Старова, 2013a, p. 761).

On the other hand, Jacqueline Derrens claims that instead of *The Path of the Eels*, the novel could be titled *The History of the Balkans*, the book that the Father dreams of writing, a book that will depict the fall of the empires from the perspective of the Balkans. The exile journey of Starova, in his corpus of work born in Albania, compared to the historical Yugoslav environment, gives a literary and poetic depiction of human destiny (Старова, 2013a, p. 763).

Following the path of the eels is the only salvation for the narrator and his family to cross to the other side of the border to escape from the new empire, Stalinism and its ideology. In this narration, it becomes evident how this new empire not only oppresses the people and their freedom of choice but also attacks nature and

wants to alter the course of the rivers. This threat is present in all the chapters of the novel which follow their destiny:

Eel of Drim... It stopped at the outflow and cried loudly: Ah, now you wretch, it's your turn! Now it's just you and me! I will show you how and where to flow. We'll even pave your banks. And we will give you new things ... [...] There is no escape, for you and your eels, who supposedly will swim off to capitalist seas and return from there!!! (Cmapова, 2013c, p. 150).

2.2. The Father's Gaze: Homeland, Memory and the "Key"

The writer conveys to the readers the intensity of everyday life relived through the inner struggles of the Father, as a main character, who constantly oscillates between the states of departure/arrival and forgetting/recalling. Starova was forced into a condition of exile where, as Amin Maalouf writes, one is compelled to think about 'where they belong, their roots, their relation with others, and the place they occupy under the sun or in the shadows' (Maalouf, 2017, p. 19). The Father, in his books describing birds and eels, "viewed the journey of the eels from a mythical and a metaphysical perspective, searching for a utopian escape... As long as humans do not disrupt the migratory circle of the birds and especially, of the eels, they will remain happy in any corner of the planet Earth" (Cmapова, 2013a, p. 57). The narrator of this novel, from the beginning, refers to his father's birthplace as the land of no return:

The gaze stopped at his birth town of Pogardec, the starting point of the last exile of his father's family in the distant year of 1942, which since then seemed to have been condemned to belong to a land of no return (p. 19).

In the journey, the "home" holds a central position and thus the symbolism of leaving the home / returning to "home" is treated through losing the place and its reconstruction. In the beginning, Starova allows the story to flow, but at one point he returns to the memories of his mother, and through the "key", which symbolizes

their departure, he builds a connection to the concept of the “home”. The idea of “home” is present in all the places they live in.

The home, in turn, is a part of a man, and even the man himself. The symbol of the “key” which represents the home in Amin Maalouf’s novel *The First Century After Beatrice*, is depicted as follows: “While I was returning all drenched, a sudden desire awoke in me to stay in the village and spend some time alone, locked in the house of my childhood. I, who came here to find a key for my door, now saw before me a door with no key!” (Maalouf, 2018, pp. 34, 38).

This symbol also holds a significant place in Starova’s novels.

If one followed the flow of mother’s memories, according to the inherited connection to the keys from the abandoned ancestral houses, the oldest key belonged to a dwelling on the shore of the Ionic Sea, whose waters splashed the homeland. [...] Mother’s key chain also had the keys of old, vanished houses...

[...]Mother also carried a key chain with keys of our return, the keys of our barren hope (CmapoBa, 2013a, p. 19).

3. Between the Lake and the Sea: Yearning and the Cursed Balkan Fate

The reason the Father is deeply engaged in studying the eels’ migration and analyzing their journey is that, although they are forced to leave and abandon their waters, they still manage, by their very nature, to return joyfully:

For a time, Father became deeply involved in studying the migratory processes in the lake, and the life of birds, fish, and insects. He was fascinated by their departure and joyful return. Could humans also adapt to these joyful migratory movements? The eels indicated the direction of the family’s fate, like a needle of the large compass of existence (2013, p. 35-36).

The Father searched through his books to find proof to convince his family—especially Mother—that their only hope lay with the eels, as they pointed

the way out of this Balkan labyrinth. But Mother always believed in staying true to the roots of the lake, while Father wanted to uproot them, to leave no matter where, the West or the East, Europe or Asia.

Mother always insisted on staying, and enduring by the blue, clear waters of the lake, while Father believed in following the water flow and now even the path of the eels. The Father's thought had one ultimate goal: returning to the land by our lake, where we left our house, the field, the vineyard, and the watermill by the small river that had flowed into the lake for eternity. Father was convinced they should return to the river's mouth at the Ionic Sea (p. 175).

When the time came for the eels to depart, Father became increasingly anxious about whether they should seek salvation in their path. He frequently asked himself: If eels know their way why have humans forgotten it? But although deep in the father's exilic soul, there was still faith and excitement for returning:

On the night of the departure of the eels he listened to his friend from the distant Russian lands sink into describing the transformation of the eels, constantly thinking about the similar fate of the people in exile. [...] I began studying the path of the eels in peace after I read all the books about the phenomenon of their migration. I did not stop studying the eels and their migration. [...] The path of the eels..., ah, the path of a barren hope of return... (Смарова, 2013, pp. 62, 115, 57).

With these thoughts and words, he accepts that it is nothing more than a barren hope. Likewise, the words of his friend Guri Poradeci: We left but we also condemned ourselves to never returning. Each with his fate motivated Father to reflect and respond to his blood brother: Ah, my brother, fate has destined us to flee. A cursed Balkan fate!...

What does it feel like to dream that, almost till the end of your life, you will remain at your birthplace, knowing that you belong there? Starova is search-

hing for the answer to that question not only in the novel *The Path of the Eels*, but also throughout the entire Balkan Saga.

In a country where political pressure persists, where people have no right to a choice, and where certain languages and religions are constantly imposed, people are forced to consider migration. In the novel *The Path of the Eels*, we can again see traces of the relationship with language, culture, and existence and dreams made up of deceptions (Chambers, 1994, p. 55).

Great suffering brother, there can be no greater! We want to escape! All of us to escape to America! And the country, a locked cage! Someone else holds the key. [...] The party has announced that on our side of the river, which flows from the lake and into the sea, and along its tributaries, they will build a power plant, raising embankments (Смарова, 2013c, p. 189).

Starova, whose identity contains many aspects, professional, ethnic background, age, and gender, which come into play when reflecting on the family saga, recounts how Turkish blood entered their family and how powerful his paternal grandmother was. He reflects on the birth of a hybrid identity within the family:

Father: My mother was of Turkish descent. God granted me a chance to live half a century with her. She was a strong woman. She lived several lives within one. For the sake of us all. [...] Her family came from a noble Turkish qadi lineage. [...] My father joyfully accepted the hand of the qadi's daughter. And so, my son, new Turkish blood flowed into our family, hastening our destiny... Ah, my son, it would take a whole century to tell the story of that Turkish mother... (2013c, p. 27-29).

The identity is not a stable category; it depends on the relationship with the Other and the understanding and communication which may be established through dialogue with the other. As Luan Starova's works demonstrate, overcoming this situation is achieved through alternative approaches, where, based on friendship and a fundamental vision of the future. By understanding the Other, a person can

resolve misunderstandings while also gaining self-awareness and personal growth. This provides a foundation to develop the theme of identity which changes and transforms, adapts to the other, and establishes a dialogue with them.

Father was the first to whisper in the night: My dear, books have destinies. Books determine destinies. I took that path and led you all with me. Only God knows whether everything will turn out well! Books offer numerous possibilities and paths to discover the Other, the different one, to gain their trust, their friendship. Didn't this happen with the books about the eels, which brought him closer and made him friends with Igor Lozinski? (Cmapova 2013a, p. 93).

What we call a way of life is an expression of national character. Naturally, protecting the values inherited from the past may sometimes face resistance. If we remember that culture is not merely a sum, but a synthesis of material and moral values, it is a scientifically proven truth that through the organic whole created by that synthesis, a dialectical struggle will emerge between the values generated by modern science and technology and the moral values inherited from a shared past, until mutual communication and balance is achieved. Culture means finding a foundation within the framework based on society and culture.

Muhammed Ali in his article Theory of ID or Identity where he explains the development of identity referred to Freud where he explains that he spoke of two equally significant processes in developing identity: (1) biological and (2) social (Ali, 2020). The first is a process of the organism that takes place within the hierarchy of all living organic systems throughout life. The second one includes living organisms that organize in groups and are defined by geographical, historical, and cultural dimensions. The Father, in the novel *The Path of the Eels*, believed that in the Balkan time, countless human lives, generations, families, and cultural identities rested within the qadi registers. With the fall of the Ottoman Empire, those re-

gisters concealed signs of a forgotten, lost life, that tried to reshape itself according to the Other, as a projection of a new identity.

The sacred books remained on the top shelf of the library, and just below were books about the Janissaries, which according to Father, contained the most complex knowledge for understanding the Balkan history. [...] Father believed that some signs from the registers could resurrect in the souls of those who lacked them so they could attain the fullness of their identity. Signs fought on the paper devoured by time, as last signals of a vanished life, carrying the ultimate message to flow into the future of their descendants. Father was there to receive them, interpret them, give them meaning, and significance, and give them life. To instigate countless families to search for the visible breaks in their continuity (Cmapova, 2013a, p. 200).

Identity is a multidimensional concept that social sciences have tried to define from different angles. When researching literature on the definition and explanation of the concept of identity or the broader question “Who am I”, this inquiry requires defining and understanding of the self (itself). The model of political organization that determines the identity politics of modern times is based on the nation-state model, built on the concept of a shared language, religion, culture, people, land, and state which are interconnected. In this model, perfection and infallibility have the same meaning as homogeneity (uniformity). When delving into the details of this homogeneity (uniformity), it is evident that it refers to a community of individuals that belong to the same nation, speak the same language, share common roots, the same religion, culture, and heritage, as well as common enemies (Erözden, 1997, p. 28).

Defining identity as “The identity makes me original and unique” or “I am not the other” emphasizes the need for the existence of others/remaining others. According to Hall (2017, p. 71); “The other belongs inside the self”. From where the self is located it can only know the Other. “I” is written in the perception of the Other. This understanding also breaks the boundaries between the internal and the

external, between those who belong and those who do not, and between those tied to a written history, and those whose history is not mentioned.

3.1. Borders and Eels as Emblems of Migration

Identity is initially formed in the imaginary realm, and only later manifests in the real world. Collective identity is realized and presented from a perspective set in the past, and not the present. As Srbinovska states: “the problem of crossing to the other side of the threshold, the other side of the border, in the direction of the so-called organized world, the world of norms and civilization” (Србиновска, 2003, p. 51-52). That’s just like the case in Luan Starova’s *Balkan Saga*. In all his work Starova draws our attention to the borders. Borders are at the center of their family in exile:

Wherever we went afterward we carried the border with us, it became a hidden part of us. In our family, after the border was set and severed our lives from Grandfather, through Grandmother, Father, Mother, and I as the narrator, we all had a piece of the border, a piece of the border within us (Старова, 2017, p. 11).

In this place, characters and objects, whose borders are marked and fixed in their basic form, enter a state of infinity. This condition and the intense intervention of the past into the present with all its intensity, obstruct the acceptance of the changes in characters and representations from the past and even becomes a reason for their rejection. The first duty of the migrant, whose present and future are shaken and in the state of expectation, is to preserve the past that was certainly experienced in its ideal form or reject it entirely. That is because according to Maalouf (2018, p. 36) the reason you came is to find a better life for yourself and your loved ones; however, if you think that the balance of power is unfavorable in regard to this expectation, fear of the unknown is added to all of this.

Do not forget, dear friend, that in the territories of the Ottoman Empire, people lived without borders for five centuries. They were close, turned to each other, and intertwined through various languages, diverse cultures, cuisines,

and customs. But in modern times, states are based precisely on borders (Cmapova, 2013b, p. 74).

Another element frequently used by Starova is the “dream”. As is well known, the dream contains time that is beyond the one we live in. It embodies an alternative reality. When analyzing the dream in these novels, we realize it serves as an escape for characters who feel they do not belong to the time and the reality they live in. At the same time, it is a place where they face the inner voice of the border and their fears, while they move to the new home they are trying to create.

Do people`s dreams divide and merge when separated by a borderline, an ordinary one, imagined, drawn by people from another time? Aunt sensed my excitement. Heavy tears rolled down her face one last time. She was the same as when she came to us, they let her cross the border only for funerals in the family. She had to have a soul that could endure the heavy burden, although the heart was constantly giving in (Cmapova, 2013b, p. 25).

Borders are merely elements that bear witness to and tell tragic Balkan stories. Every Balkan individual has, at least once, passed through the storm of the border within themselves. During this crossing, generations were left with an enigma of the future and a newly transformed identity. Once you step to the other side of the border, you are faced with a sad shadow of long-lasting uncertainty. Living two lives, the emigrant, leaves behind, on the other side of the border, a life that will always whisper to them, while they, with their loyalty, wait to be accepted into the margins of others.

In his book *Borders*, published in 2017, Starova remains true to the title and explains the borders within his family. According to Grandfather, the border was not just a marked line in the space. I was something bigger and deeper, essential to understand and interpret (Starova, 2017, p. 32). However, Starova further elaborates on the term border from five different perspectives: those of the Grandfather, Grandmother, Mother, and Father and in the end, his own perspective, as the family`s grandchild and son.

We will present two different sentiments from the book from two perspectives not mentioned in the previously analyzed novels. In this work, Starova defines the term border from the point of the view of Grandfather and Grandmother and their memories:

Our lives, young and old, became marked by the border. One could even say that we, in time, turned into border people, wherever destiny led us. Every family member had their share of stories about the border throughout the twentieth century. No matter how different they were from one another, every story was incorporated into the bigger narrative for the border, connecting several generations marked by its existence (2017, p. 14).

These words are the very reason Starova decided to give this title to his book. Through Grandfather's stories, the narrator reflects on the border in the following way:

According to Grandfather's account, our family had long been marked by the migratory fate of the Albanian people, by the life with old and new borders, by the border life. [...] Grandfather could be considered a kind of storyteller and chronicler of people's fates, the border, of that new miracle of the Balkans (2017, p. 23)

These words – that their lives, young and old, had become marked by the border – underscore the profound significance of borders in Starova's work and provide the impetus for the book's very title. Starova utilizes his grandfather's narratives as a lens through which to examine the intricate workings and enduring consequences of borders, both literal and metaphorical. It is through the grandfather's stories that the narrator reflects on the profound and formative impact of borders on his family's trajectory, a fate deeply intertwined with the migratory experiences of the Albanian people. According to the grandfather's perspective, as recounted by Starova, the family's history has long been marked by the migratory fate of the Albanian people, by the life with old and new borders, by the border life. The grandfather emerges as a kind of chronicler, a figure who not

only recounts the past but also embodies its impact on the present. He becomes, in Starova's portrayal, a storyteller and chronicler of people's fates, the border, of that new miracle of the Balkans. The border, for the Grandfather, is also an imagined community, and he passes this on as "inheritance" to be observed and respected. As such, Starova's grandfather becomes a vessel through which the novel suggests that the very act of remembering, interpreting, and transmitting these stories becomes a crucial act of cultural preservation and resistance against the forces of erasure and displacement. This act is a sign of the novel's intent to preserve and commemorate a family history threatened by political and geographic instability, for indeed, he sensed that the new century would be the century of Balkan borders.

Then we come to Grandmother's story, who in her life became a bridge between Constantinople and the Balkans. In this part of the book, we can observe an intertextual element at the beginning of the novel *Fortress of Ash* where he recounts his Grandmother's dream where she speaks with Fethi Okyar Bey about Father's fate, whether he should stay or return to Constantinople. "However, we will cite a passage where Father, using the memories of borders, is trying to open the 'locked doors' of the past – a symbolic act that attempts to access and understand his family's complex relationship with identity and displacement. This suggests a tension, an urge to be able to cross what is not able to be crossed, for he has been trying to open these doors for 60 years. The legacy of the border, as a lived experience, falls heavily on Grandmother, but also on Father, as the eldest son and 'pillar of the family.' The passage hints at a prior history of displacement. The burden of memory passes to the father and the grandmother, but also indicates that prior to this burden being passed, there was still one door or border to cross, for the grandmother:

Grandfather left the burden of the border especially to Grandmother, but also to Father, as the eldest son, the pillar of the family. Poor Grandmother was already marked by borders even before she got married. In the bloom of her youth, her mother, brothers, and sisters left for Constantinople, after

they sold off the properties in Rumelia for a good price, and bought new, even bigger ones in Izmir and Constantinople. [...] I write to open a long-closed door, to cross the border. I have been trying to open the door, to cross the border for no less than sixty years. Forever etched in my consciousness are the words of my Grandmother, of Ottoman, Turkish, and Balkan descent: Açkapi! Open the door! (2017, p. 69-70).

The text emphasizes the inheritance of trauma and the desire to open up a new world, though through old and worn doors. The Turkish phrase “Aç kapi! Open the door!” is not only an entreaty, but a symbol of accessing a past that continues to haunt the present. It echoes Walter Benjamin’s understanding of history, where past traumas continually seek recognition and redress (Benjamin, 1968). The father and grandmother, weighed down by the legacy of borders, are both seeking to “open the door,” attempting to find resolution or understanding within the confines of their shared, and inherited, history.

No borders can last forever or exist in the same place. They change with the fall of empires or the change of different ideologies, but at that moment they also leave many victims on both sides of the border:

Yet, there will always be one last border that will defy all others. A border beyond borders! Which border is that, Father? Isn't it the human being itself? Maybe you're right, son, I always search for borders within myself, in my thoughts, but it is hard to find the exit from those borders until they become a reality (2017, p. 59).

Despite all the emotions, hopes, and frustrations, this family *never figured out how many borders they should cross, nor did they discover the path to return to their homeland (2017, p. 15).*

In the novel *The Path of the Eels*, the author in a similar way, but from a different point of view, depicts the tragic history of his family. The path that the eels take symbolizes the movement of the uprooted families in different directions, as they experience exclusion from one and adaptation to another, new culture. Their

identities become fragmented giving rise to a desire to create an identity compatible with the environment they find themselves in at the given historical moment. According to Starova, in his narrative, through the harmony between nature and mankind, the path that eels take should symbolize people's journey during their migration and return home.

In these returns or their new "homes," they are constantly under pressure from the questions "Who are they" and "Where do they belong". The traditions we inherit such as the culture, history, and language, cannot be destroyed. They may be fragmented, opened up to questioning, and, thus, connected to the different circumstances in which communities, families, or, the person find themselves:

*[...] One had to follow the uncertain path of the eels,
To continue along the Father's path,
To search for the reasons and meaning
Of this great Balkan illusion (Cmapova, 2013a, p. 32).*

Through these experiences and movements – the constant negotiation of migration, adaptation, and the burden of history – the "self" is constantly shaped and reexamined (Chambers, 2014, p. 44). The profound pressure exerted by political forces on the father, a central figure in Starova's narratives, is palpable in the dialogue between the father and Guri Poradeci, a scene revealing the desperation and confinement experienced by those living under a totalitarian regime. This is not simply political, but a deeply personal turmoil for the "self". As Ian Chambers argues, migration creates a space of "cultural translation," where individuals are forced to navigate between different worlds and grapple with fragmented identities (Chambers, 1994). The dialogue highlights this sense of entrapment:

Tell me, brother, what troubles you? Let's set aside other hardships. A great trouble brother, none greater! We should all flee to America! And the country, a locked cage! Others keep the key. Who keeps the key brother? – Father leaned in. Still Stalin, my brother. The Party has sent word to our side

of the river, which flows from the lake into the sea...[...] Cursed, cursed is every departure from the homeland brother! Even more cursed is when they take your hope in the homeland...we seek hope in leaving (2013b, p. 189, 191).

This cry for escape encapsulates the sense of the homeland transformed into a “locked cage”, where freedom is controlled by an external force. For Chambers, such experiences of displacement and confinement create a “borderline” existence, a space where individuals are caught between the desire to belong and the impossibility of fully integrating into a new or former context. Thus, as is argued in the framework of Chambers, the longing to escape is paradoxically twinned with the recognition that they carry a sense of loss and cultural trauma. This shows the tragic fate of the characters of fleeing to another state, as that does not solve the problem, but instead takes the place of the original. In the novel, the father comes to be haunted by the words of his friend, which then reflect upon his history and his life in general.

4. CONCLUSION

Exile, as a word, expresses loneliness, a hard life, and a burden on the soul. Due to this, people in exile, in a possible world, are always worried that their current homes are only temporary dwellings. The borders that define the security of the country they find themselves in, may also feel like prison. A foreign land, nostalgia, and insecurity that comes with migration, an undeniable reality of the world, are significant themes in literature. The result of this, according to the outcome of the novel before us, unfolds as an entity of the foreigner, the self as the other, the remaining one. Migration, which is a forced change of place, and severing of ties, is a matter of changing one’s dwelling. A dwelling signifies an environment created by memory, recollections, language, ego, identity, and history. Changing this environment means leaving everything behind, and creating a new life, a new language, and a new identity in a foreign setting. It means putting down new roots.

As a social phenomenon “migration” is as old as human history. Throughout history, natural disasters, insufficient resources, hopes, and aspirations for

a better life, including wars have been the main causes of migration. Essentially, migrants face two classical questions they carry within themselves: Why are you here? and when will you return home?

No migrant knows the answer to the second question until it is asked. Only then, deep inside, they realize they may never return. Migrations, which are difficult to erase from the social and individual memory, create numerous problems—social, psychological, and economic—that affect everything from education to housing. For this reason, the memories of migrants are filled with pain and tears. Identity is a widely studied term, but retains its significance in the field, especially due to increased human mobility. Throughout history, the relationship between migration and its concepts has shaped different identities. In his works, Luan Starova describes one Balkan story through the fall of empires, where his memories are identified with the notion of the border. They move through homes and cities, people, events, and the entire homeland he bore with him throughout the exile. We explore the traumatic reflection of the self, the language, the cultures of the Balkans, and departure and return in the novel *The Path of the Eels*, which introduces the narrator's thoughts on new migration and exile, specifically the journey to America. The book presents a comprehensive depiction of the reasons for migration, illustrated through selected situations in the form of memories/ autobiographies or autofiction, and novels. It also delves into the circumstances of the transformation, when one identity is lost, another emerges within the space of living between languages and culture.

Several elements explored in this particular novel, such as keys, borders, identities symbolize the perpetual search for rediscovering of oneself and creating connection with new dwelling, even though the migrant status remains the most prefunded identity. Similarly, the process of permanent mobility occurs to the eelsthat make such a long journey to reach the Ohrid lake which is the starting point of Starova's family destiny.

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